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YEAR 2021-2022

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Introduction

Bishnupur (also spelled as Vishnupur) is a community development block (CD block) that forms an administrative division in Bishnupur subdivision of Bankura district in West Bengal, India. Bishnupur CD block is located at 23°05'00"N 87°19'00"E in the north-eastern part of the district and belongs to the fertile low lying alluvial plains, similar to the predominating rice lands in adjacent districts of West Bengal. Here, the eye constantly rests on wide expanses of rice fields, green in the rains but parched and dry in summer. This block is surrounded by Sonamukhi CD block on the north; Indas, Patrasayer and Joypur on the east; Garhbeta I CD block in Paschim Medinipur district on the south and Taldangra and Onda CD blocks on the west. Bishnupur block has an area of 365.73 km². It has 1 panchayat samity, 9 gram panchayats, 113 gram sansads (village councils), 161 mouzas and 147 inhabited villages. Gram panchayats of Bishnupur block/panchayat samiti are: Ajodhya, Bankadha, Belsulia, Bhora, Dwarika Gosainpur, Layekbandh, Marar, Radhanagar and Uliara.

The annual average rainfall is 1067 mm. The soil type varies from sandy to lateritic and gravelly soils as well as heavy clay soils. Use of fertilizer, improved seeds, organic manure and pesticides are increasing day by day. Farmers have now been habituated to use agricultural implements like tractor, power tiller, thresher, pump set, sprayer etc. in the field of agriculture. Paddy transplanter, paddy reaper, drum seeder etc. has recently been introduced.

Rice is the main crop of the district as well as Bishnupur block. Besides rice, the major crops are potato, wheat, vegetables, mustard, summer sesame etc. Though the block is prone to drought, it can raise surplus food production in years of good rainfall.

Water scarcity due to climate change like increase in temperature and decrease in rainfall is an increasingly important issue in many parts of the world. Restricted supply of good quality water is the most important factor limiting the crop production. On the other hand, owing to over exploitation, the ground water in many parts of the country is fast depleting. Thus, efficient management of water resources through increased irrigation efficiency is essential to meet the increasing competition for water between agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. During last few decades, emphasis has been given on alternative water application method such as micro irrigation which may contribute substantially to attain the twin objectives of higher productivity and optimum use of water. The trend in recent years has been towards conversion of surface to micro irrigation because cost of installation has relatively decreased with the easy access to subsidized micro irrigation equipment's. We therefore are trying to give special emphasis on sprinkler irrigation technique through Bangla Krishi Sech Yojana (BKSY) in different crops cultivated throughout Bishnupur block.

Bksy In Brief

The Government of West Bengal has launched Bangla Krishi Sech Yojana to provide necessary assistance to small and marginal farmers to promote micro irrigation facilities which will ensure that the farmers can cultivate their land using less amount of water mainly in areas receiving less rainfall. It is important to note that small and marginal farmers can't afford the cost of drip and sprinkle irrigation techniques as they cost around Rs. 70,000 and Rs. 20,000 per acre of land respectively. But in this scheme farmers will get these facilities absolutely free of

cost excluding GST. Bankura district in the state of West Bengal has been doing consistently sterling work in the execution of Bangla Krishi Sech Yojana (BKSY) for quite some time as discovered during interaction with the local farmers, inspection of actual works in the field and a random inspection of the records as readily available. In this regard, Bishnupur block of Bankura district is not an exception. The block has moved in a very methodical and planned manner to execute this type of certain very good scheme with respect to the identified focus areas.

During the financial year of 2021-2022, total 46 installations of sprinkler irrigation system were done successfully in Dwarika-Gossainpur (33) and Morar (13) gram panchayats almost covering 13 hectares of land. Registration, joint inspection, work order as well as installation were accordingly planned, made and executed with a very strong system of monitoring and supervision backed by block, sub-division and also district level which added to the overall quality of the scheme.

Achievement Story

Smt. Shyamali Singha (58) is a well-known progressive farmer from Kharikasuli mouza (Plot No. 44, JL. No. 119 and Khatian No. 212), Morar gram panchayat of Bishnupur block, Bankura district. She has been involved in farming since the age of 20. From the beginning itself, she was keen to learn and adopt new production techniques. This passion led her to adopt sprinkler irrigation system when it was introduced in agriculture in our state through BKSY. Previously she was using conventional surface irrigation method for cultivating crops. But after she gained knowledge about micro irrigation techniques from television and newspaper, she became quite interested about adoption of this new method in her field. She got an automated sprinkler irrigation system on 20/04/2022 from Government of West Bengal, installed for cultivation in her farm. Presently, she is cultivating groundnut on 0.08 hectares of land using micro irrigation.

Officials from the office of Assistant Director of Agriculture, Bishnupur block visited her field recently and when she was asked about the advantages of this improved irrigation method she is getting over previously used surface method, she replied enthusiastically that one of the greatest irrigation methods that have been invented for taking care of plants in a proper way is sprinkler irrigation. She also added that when you witness rainfalls you must have seen how droplets of water get distributed equally among all the crops that have been planted in an individual field. The plants seem to come back to life because of gaining a sufficient amount of water after each rainfall occurrence. The most appreciable regions, which have witnessed a critical change, have been noticed in saving of the most precious input i.e. 'water'; equal distribution and controlled application of water depending on the actual necessity and requirements of plants.

Not only Smt. Shyamali Singha but also many other farmers of that mouza including Shri Panchanan Ghosh, Shri Sudhamadhab Goswami, Shri Mahabbat Mandal, Shri Banshi Singha, Shri Anarul Mondal have applied for getting sprinkler irrigation system. According to

Shri Banshi Singha they have always watched on television the success of micro irrigation in crop fields only in Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh etc. but they are now capable of adopting this technique easily like other states by the extreme co-operation from our government. Besides, it was added by him that there is no requirement of using many areas of our field for setting up the sprinkler irrigation; the interference with cultivation for setting up this system is very less and frequent application of water can be supplied to the plants which you will not need to do it yourself.

Shri Anarul Mondal said that the sprinkler irrigation is suitable for setting up in all types of soil and this system can be used for other purposes as well such as cooling during high temperature, protection from insect pests etc. They are highly determined to use micro irrigation in their fields for cultivating various types of crops in future.

The disadvantage of this system i.e. the investment cost required for purchasing the equipment of sprinkler irrigation system is high which can be overcome by the marked assistance of full subsidy from the government and only minimum amount of GST has to be paid by the farmers.

Just like how rainfall distributes water, sprinkler irrigation is a system that allows water distribution through the pipes by pumping and with the help of sprinklers the water is sprinkled into the air. The water is then converted into small droplets like rain which then falls on the crops in a field. This water saving method seems to be a mind-blowing technology that will ease farming and also increase the yield of the crop. Their plan for the future is to expand the area of cultivation for crops that witness good yields.

The overall outcomes of the various works executed, as mentioned above, are really very encouraging and prove as to how a committed and determined effort can bring about positive changes by way of efficient and effective implementation of a government scheme.

Groundnut is an important oilseed crop in India as well as our state. Surface irrigation is the prevalent irrigation method followed in this crop. Micro irrigation viz. sprinkler irrigation in groundnut is a relatively new innovative technology which has convincingly shown that the technique results in high water use efficiency, conserves water and energy, reduces fertilizer requirement, provides better quality crop and higher pod yield and moreover increases profits. However, if not installed properly, it may result in wastage of water, time and yield. Application of micro irrigation requires careful study of all the relevant factors like land topography, soil, water, crop and agro-climatic conditions, and suitability of micro irrigation system and its components. The subsidy and technical support to the farmers may be an incentive to adopt this method on a large scale. Adoption of sprinkler irrigation system in

groundnut cultivation is technically feasible and economically viable and needs to be vigorously followed.

The entire team for documenting and skilfully depicting the success stories of different farmers of Bishnupur Block by visiting their fields where sprinkler irrigation systems has been successfully installed during 2021-2022 is being complimented and congratulated by the office of Assistant Director of Agriculture, Bishnupur Block, Bankura. Further, these success stories would go a long way to encourage other farmers to adopt this improved methodology and enhance their income and moreover these are truly the stories of innovators in farming who are making a difference in this agricultural industry, starting with their own operations.